

Contamination Budget: Trade-offs between Breadth, Depth and Difficulty (Supplementary Material)

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Abstract

Contamination in large language models (LLMs), and machine learning more broadly, refers to the inclusion of equal –or very similar– examples in both training and test sets. This phenomenon usually translates into better test performance. Here we explore when this contamination is performed intentionally, for purposes that can be malicious (e.g., get better scores in evaluations) or benevolent (e.g., fix some mistakes). These interventions, usually in the form of fine-tuning memorisations, come with a *budget* in the size of the fine-tuning dataset. Several trade-offs appear between the breadth of the intervention (how many examples to be memorised), its depth (how many repetitions of each example) and the difficulty of the examples. By studying several LLMs and datasets, we observe some monotonic behaviour (more difficult items require more depth to be ‘fixed’) but also some non-monotonic phenomena (very high depth levels have negative effects on non-contaminated examples). This suggests that trade-offs should be found not only in terms of the budget but also according to model specifics, the task and the item difficulty at hand.

A Supplementary Material

This supplementary material serves as technical appendix for the paper *Contamination Budget: Trade-offs between Breadth, Depth and Difficulty* [Mehrbaikhsh et al., 2025] published in the 34th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI 2025). Here we include detailed proofs of theoretical claims, sample prompts used in our experiments, out-of-distribution extra results and model-level results for each benchmark.

B Proofs

In this appendix, we provide the detailed proof that, under the assumption that each example requires the same minimum number of repetitions r^* to be fixed, the strategy described in Equation 2 maximises the expected validity in Equation 1 given the budget b .

Consider:

- Let \mathcal{X} and $p(x_i)$ a probability over them.
- Let m be the large language model before fine-tuning.
- Let $v(x_i, m(x_i)) \in \{0, 1\}$ denote the validity of the model’s output for instance x_i .
- Let $f_i^m(r)$ denote the function mapping the number of repetitions r used for fine-tuning on instance x_i to the validity after fine-tuning.
- Assume that $f_i^m(r)$ is a step function:

$$f_i^m(r) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } r < r^* \\ 1, & \text{if } r \geq r^* \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

indicating that each instance requires exactly r^* repetitions to be fixed.

- Let b be the total budget for fine-tuning, representing the total number of repetitions available.
- Since we are interested in the instances where the model is initially wrong ($v(x_i, m(x_i)) = 0$), we consider only those instances in our allocation, as allocating repetitions to instances already correct ($x_i, v(m(x_i)) = 1$) would not improve expected validity. We assume all other instances not used in the contamination are not affected.

Claim: The expected validity V (Eq. 1) is maximised by allocating $r_i = r^*$ repetitions to each and every example.

Proof: We proceed by contradiction. Assume that there exists an optimal allocation that does not follow the above strategy. Then, in this allocation, there must exist at least two instances x_i and x_j such that: $p(x_i) > p(x_j)$, $r_i < r^*$ (so $v(x_i, m(x_i)) = 0$), and $r_j \geq r^*$ (so $v(x_j, m(x_j)) = 1$).

Since x_i has a higher probability than x_j , we can increase the expected validity by reallocating resources from x_j to x_i . Specifically, we can decrease r_j by r^* (setting $r'_j = r_j - r^*$) and increase r_i by r^* (setting $r'_i = r_i + r^*$). Because the minimal number of repetitions required to fix an instance is r^* , reducing r_j by r^* (to r'_j) will make $v(x_j, m(x_j)) = 0$, and increasing r_i by r^* (to r'_i) will make $v(x_i, m(x_i)) = 1$.

The change in expected validity due to this reallocation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V &= [p(x_i) \cdot v'(m(x_i)) + p(x_j) \cdot v'(m(x_j))] - & (4) \\ & [p(x_i) \cdot v(m(x_i)) + p(x_j) \cdot v(m(x_j))] \\ &= [p(x_i) \cdot 1 + p(x_j) \cdot 0] - [p(x_i) \cdot 0 + p(x_j) \cdot 1] \\ &= p(x_i) - p(x_j) \\ &> 0, & (5) \end{aligned}$$

since $p(x_i) > p(x_j)$. Therefore, reallocating repetitions from x_j to x_i increases the expected validity V , contradicting the assumption that the original allocation was optimal.

This contradiction implies that in any optimal allocation, we cannot have an instance with a higher probability unfixed (i.e., $r_i < r^*$) while a lower probability instance is fixed (i.e., $r_j \geq r^*$). \square

C Prompts

Table 4 provides examples of instances from each of the benchmarks used in our study (§4.1).

Benchmark	Sample Prompt
MMLU-Pro	Please answer the following question by choosing the correct option. Question: What does Australia have in common with the rest of the world during the Holocene epoch? Options: A. the emergence of complex social hierarchies and political systems B. a growth in cultural diversity C. the formation of a single global civilization D. the onset of a new ice age E. the introduction of farming from neighboring continents F. the complete extinction of megafauna G. the independent domestication of wheat and cattle Correct option: B. a growth in cultural diversity
Anagram	Rearrange the following anagram into an English word: "itcepsn". Answer: inspect
MedMCQA	Please answer the following question by choosing the correct option. Question: The most common etiological agent for acute bronchiolitis in infancy is? Options: A. Influenza virus B. Para influenza virus C. Rhinovirus D. Respiratory syncytial virus Correct option: D. Respiratory syncytial virus
Addition	6919 + 71945 = 78864

Table 4: Examples of instances from each of the benchmarks used in our study.

D Out-of-distribution results

We evaluated the models on out-of-distribution (OOD) data to assess the extent of contamination effects on unrelated tasks. Figure 6 complements Figure 4 in the main text showing the aggregated performance of models on further combinations of datasets for fine-tuning and posterior evaluation.

Figure 6: Out-of-distribution aggregated performance of the models listed in Table 1, fine-tuned on the (D_f) subset of one dataset and evaluated on the (D_t) subset from another dataset included in our study. The figure displays the overall performance on D_t (represented by the 'All items' plots), as well as the performance across different difficulty bins.

E Model-level results

We provide detailed performance results at the model level for each benchmark in §4.1 to offer more nuanced insights into how different architectures and sizes of LLMs respond to the different contamination interventions performed.

E.1 MMLU-pro

Figure 7 shows the performance of LLMs in Table 1 on the MMLU-Pro benchmark. Each figure illustrates the overall performance of the fine-tuned models on the test set (D_t), the fine-tuning set (D_f), the non-contaminated set (D_u), and the validation set (D_v), as well as performance across difficulty bins. Baseline results (non-finetuned models) are also shown.

Figure 7: Performance of models in Table 1 on the test set (D_t , dots), fine-tuning set (D_f , bars), non-contaminated set (D_u , bars) and validation set (D_v , connected dots) of MMLU-Pro. The figure illustrates the overall performance on D_t ("All items" plots) as well as the performance of the models across five difficulty bins.

E.2 Anagram

Figure 8 shows the performance of LLMs in Table 1 on the Anagram benchmark. Each figure illustrates the overall performance of the fine-tuned models on the test set (D_t), the fine-tuning set (D_f), the non-contaminated set (D_u), and the validation set (D_v), as well as performance across difficulty bins. Baseline results (non-finetuned models) are also shown.

Figure 8: Performance of models in Table 1 on the test set (D_t , dots), fine-tuning set (D_f , bars), non-contaminated set (D_u , bars) and validation set (D_v , connected dots) of Anagram. The figure illustrates the overall performance on D_t ("All items" plots) as well as the performance of the models across five difficulty bins.

E.3 Addition

Figure 9 shows the performance of LLMs in Table 1 on the Addition benchmark. Each figure illustrates the overall performance of the fine-tuned models on the test set (D_t), the fine-tuning set (D_f), the non-contaminated set (D_u), and the validation set (D_v), as well as performance across difficulty bins. Baseline results (non-finetuned models) are also shown. For the Addition benchmark we have included three more scenarios, s_167 , s_250 and s_500 . This allows us to see the results for the deepest case where the whole budget is spent on a single instance. We did not include these three scenarios in our main study because $\mathbb{E}[n_j]$ is less than one and this does not allow us to clearly study the role of difficulty in these cases.

Figure 9: Performance of models in Table 1 on the test set (D_t , dots), fine-tuning set (D_f , bars), non-contaminated set (D_u , bars) and validation set (D_v , connected dots) of Addition. The figure illustrates the overall performance on D_t ("All items" plots) as well as the performance of the models across five difficulty bins.

E.4 MedMCQA

Figure 10 shows the performance of LLMs in Table 1 on the MedMCQA benchmark. Each figure illustrates the overall performance of the fine-tuned models on the test set (D_t), the fine-tuning set (D_f), the non-contaminated set (D_u), and the validation set (D_v), as well as performance across difficulty bins. Baseline results (non-finetuned models) are also shown.

Figure 10: Performance of models in Table 1 on the test set (D_t , dots), fine-tuning set (D_f , bars), non-contaminated set (D_u , bars) and validation set (D_v , connected dots) of MedMCQA. The figure illustrates the overall performance on D_t ("All items" plots) as well as the performance of the models across five difficulty bins.

F Effects of difficulty

Figure 11 shows the aggregated performance of all fine-tuned models on the test set D_t for each task, stratified across five difficulty bins. These bins range from the easiest (Bin 1) to the hardest (Bin 5) items. The figure illustrates how the accuracy of the models varies with increasing contamination depth r_i and across different item difficulty levels.

Table 5 complements this analysis by showing the correlation coefficients between difficulty levels and aggregated performance across contamination scenarios for each task when tested on D_t . Negative correlations indicate a decrease in performance with increasing difficulty.

Figure 11: Aggregated performance of all fine-tuned models on test set (D_t) for each task across 5 difficulty bins.

In general, the models perform well on easier items in D_t (including both contaminated and non-contaminated items), showing significant accuracy with minimal repetitions. However, as the difficulty increases, more repetitions yield diminishing returns.

	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_5	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{20}	s_{40}	s_{60}	s_{80}	s_{100}
Anagram	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.99	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.97	-0.93	-0.93	-0.93	-0.94
Addition	-1.00	-1.00	-0.99	-0.99	-0.99	-0.99	-0.99	-1.00	-0.99	-0.99	-0.99	-1.00	-1.00	-0.99	-1.00
MMLU-Pro	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-0.99	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-0.99
MedMCQA	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-0.99	-1.00	-0.99	-0.99	-1.00	-1.00	-0.99	-1.00	-1.00

Table 5: Correlations of difficulty levels with performance across different scenarios for each task when tested on D_t .

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge support from: Grant for Master Studies funded by ValgrAI – Valencian Graduate School and Research Network for Artificial Intelligence and Generalitat Valenciana; granted by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF, EU; CIPROM/2022/6 (FASSLOW) and IDIFEDER/2021/05 (CLUSTERIA) funded by Generalitat Valenciana; and Spanish grant PID2021-122830OB-C42 (SFERA) funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and “ERDF A way of making Europe”.

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